

Continuous wet oxidation of hydrothermal liquefaction aqueous phase: oxidant supply and integration potential

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ABSTRACT

Hydrothermal Liquefaction (HTL) is a promising technology for biomass valorization, but effective treatment of the aqueous byproduct presents an unresolved challenge. Wet oxidation (WO) offers a potential solution to provide heat for a future integrated process and produce large amounts of biogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂). This study investigates non-catalytic WO in a continuous flow reactor for treating the HTL aqueous phase (HTL-AP) derived from cattle manure and wheat straw, focusing on oxidation efficiency and degradation products. To explore thermal integration potential, the WO process was operated at residence times (12–45 min) and reaction temperatures (350–365 °C) resembling those of HTL. For the first time, different stoichiometric ratios (0.5–2 times the chemical oxygen demand (COD)) were evaluated, using air and hydrogen peroxide as oxidants. WO using air at 350 °C removed 64–85 % of COD and total organic carbon (TOC) and showed almost complete degradation of nitrogen-containing components to ammonium at the most severe conditions. Increasing air beyond stoichiometric oxygen demand had little effect, while enhanced oxidation efficiency was shown for WO with increasing supply of hydrogen peroxide. Acetic acid accumulated under sub-stoichiometric conditions of hydrogen peroxide but degraded with increased oxidant supply. Gas analysis confirmed almost pure CO₂ streams for sub-stoichiometric hydrogen peroxide WO, while WO with air resulted in a nitrogen diluted off-gas, supporting the implications for future use of the biogenic CO₂ for Power-2-x or sequestration applications. Overall, the results show the feasibility for HTL-AP valorization using WO and highlight its potential for integration with HTL.

1. Introduction

Regarding climate change and global warming, the transportation sector stands out as a key contributor, accounting for around 23 % of the global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in 2022 [1]. Therefore, decarbonizing this sector is a crucial step in reducing global carbon dioxide emissions. Renewable fuel production from biomass is widely regarded as a key alternative to fossil fuels in the transportation sector, particularly for high-power applications such as shipping and aviation [2]. Hydrothermal Liquefaction (HTL) is a thermochemical conversion technology that has gained growing attention for transforming abundant biomass into an energy-dense organic phase, termed biocrude. The HTL process operates at moderate temperature and high pressure (250–374 °C, 4–22 MPa) and is suitable for various biomass feedstocks with dry matter (DM) contents between 5 and 35 % [3]. HTL resembles the formation of natural fossil fuel, generating four products: bio-crude, aqueous phase (HTL-AP), gas phase and solid phase [4]. Bio-crude is the

desired main product, which can be utilized as drop-in fuel after upgrading [5]. The resulting AP contains 20–50 % of the initial feedstock carbon. Due to the low DM content of the initial HTL feedstock slurry (15–25 wt%), large volumes of HTL-AP are generated [6]. The HTL-AP contains excessive organic loadings, evident from its high Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) in the range of 10–90 g_{O2}/L [7]. This presents a major burden to treat before disposal, but it can also be seen as an untapped resource of energy and value-added chemicals [8]. The composition of the AP depends on the initial feedstock, but broadly consists of alcohols, carboxylic acids, ketones, phenols and nitrogen containing components [6,9,10]. Several technologies for HTL-AP treatment and valorization have been investigated, including anaerobic digestion, electrochemical oxidation, algae growth, microbial systems, hydrothermal gasification, recirculation or aqueous phase reforming [7,8,11–14]. Another potential HTL-AP treatment method emerging in recent years is the exothermic wet oxidation (WO) process.

WO presents an effective treatment method for highly contaminated

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or toxic wastewater streams [15] with COD ranges preferably between 20 and 200 g_{O₂}/L [16]. During WO, the degradation of organic species takes place in water and an oxidative atmosphere, degrading organics to carbon dioxide and therefore reducing COD. Typical process conditions for subcritical WO include temperatures between 125 and 350 °C and pressures above the vapor pressure of water [17]. By applying high pressure, the liquid phase is maintained and the solubility of oxygen in aqueous solutions is enhanced, leading to increased reaction rates and production of free radicals [18]. The degree of oxidation depends on temperature, oxygen partial pressure, residence time and susceptibility to oxidation of the respective component. Organic components are either totally oxidized to carbon dioxide, water and ammonium or partially to low molecular weight intermediates (e. g. acetic acid) [18]. One advantage of the process is that recalcitrant organic components are mostly destroyed and not converted from the liquid to gas or solid phase [19]. Oxidants applied can be in gaseous (e. g. air, pure oxygen) or liquid form (e. g. hydrogen peroxide) [20]. Both types of oxidants undergo two main stages that influence oxidation reaction [19,21]: First is a physical stage, where gases require gas-liquid transfer, while liquid oxidants involve a simpler liquid-liquid mixing. The second stage is the chemical oxidation process, driven by radical reactions. Non-catalytic WO primarily follows a free radical chain mechanism, with organic hydroperoxides playing a key role [22]. Debellefontaine et al. [18] proposed a simplified reaction scheme for wet air oxidation, where the particular role of acetic acid as main intermediate byproduct is highlighted. Organic species in aqueous solution are initially oxidized to hydroperoxides, before being further degraded to alcohols or ketones and aldehydes. From this stage, the organic components are further oxidized partially to acetic acid as main intermediate or totally to carbon dioxide and water as final oxidation products.

A limited number of studies have investigated WO of HTL-AP recently, mainly focusing on improving the oxidation efficiency and optimizing the production of value-added chemicals such as acetic acid. Kilgore et al. conducted a catalyst screening study for WO using air in batch reactors and subsequently applied some catalysts to continuous trickle bed experiments, observing a COD reduction of 50 % and an increase in acetic acid concentration of 40 % [23]. Catalytic WO of HTL-AP derived from woody biomass removed up to 76 % of COD by applying temperatures between 50 and 90 °C and hydrogen peroxide as oxidant in the presence of FeO- and N-doped char as catalyst, as reported by Tews et al. [24]. Vadlamudi et al. studied the effect of temperature and pH on the WO of HTL-AP from poultry manure and observed increased oxidation efficiency of organic species in an acidic environment [25]. Silva Thomsen et al. investigated WO with oxygen of HTL-AP derived from sewage sludge in batch operation, reporting mainly acetic acid and ammonium as final products between 200 and 350 °C and almost complete degradation at the most severe conditions of 350 °C and 180 min residence time [10]. In another study, Silva Thomsen et al. investigated WO in continuous mode with process conditions similar to HTL (300–350 °C; 6–50 min) and an excess air supply of 1.5–2 times the stoichiometric oxygen demand, achieving COD reductions of up to 95 %, increased acetic acid and ammonium shares and an energy consumption reduction of 40 % due to the exothermic reaction [26]. The possibility of recovering heat from the exothermic WO reaction is interesting in the HTL-WO context, considering the heat demand of the HTL process.

However, the effect of supplied oxidant type and ratio vs. COD, especially at sub-stoichiometric conditions in continuous WO reactors have so far not been the target of scientific research, despite their importance for future integration scenarios of HTL-WO and carbon dioxide utilization. This is particularly important when considering the use of the produced CO₂, where residual oxygen and nitrogen could be detrimental for further exploitation to e-fuels or sequestration. Additionally, reaction temperatures above 350 °C are important to investigate when focusing on the thermal integration of HTL with WO. Utilizing the exothermicity of WO could lead to autothermal operation of HTL-WO, but to achieve this, the WO outlet temperature must exceed

the HTL operating temperature. The current study addresses these gaps in the literature to advance the application of HTL-AP treatment with WO and the integration of HTL and WO technologies. Specifically, we investigate the effect of different oxidants at varying stoichiometric ratios, temperatures and residence times to evaluate the effect on oxidation efficiency, byproducts and gas composition with the target for future process integration.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Continuous wet oxidation reactor

Wet oxidation experiments were carried out in a continuous plug flow reactor custom built from 23.15 m Sanicro35 pipes and 316 stainless steel fittings with 6 mm inner and 8 mm outer diameter and a total volume of approximately 880 mL. The HTL-AP was placed on a balance and introduced via an MT8 metering pump (Wanner HydraCell, USA) at different flow rates to obtain the desired residence times. Air was compressed using an air-driven booster pump (model GBT7/30 USUN, China) and inserted to the reactor before the first heat exchanger. The desired air flow rate was either manually regulated with a needle valve or automatically by a mass flow controller (Brooks instruments, model SLA5850).

The tube in tube heat exchanger section is designed as two 1.85 and 1.12 m length countercurrent concentric pipes with an internal diameter of 6 mm of the inner pipe and 14 mm of the outer pipe. The cold incoming HTL-AP and air mixture is heated up by the outgoing hot treated AP and air stream by entering the inner pipe in heat exchanger 1 and the outer shell in heat exchanger 2. This specific design ensures that residence times for hot and cold side remain comparable, considering different volumes in the inner and outer tube. After being preheated, the feed enters the trim heater section consisting of two 1.15 m tubes, where the final reaction temperature is reached. The desired reaction temperature is maintained in the main reactor section, composed of four tubes with a total length of 9.9 m. After passing through this main section, the treated stream, hereafter referred to as WO-AP, is cooled by the HTL-AP inlet in the heat exchanger. The temperature of WO-AP is further reduced in a water cooler before reaching the back pressure regulator (H62 Equilibar, USA) which is protected by a filter element (Hy-Lok FT, pore size 50 µm). The WO-AP stream is finally directed to a product tank, where the aqueous fraction is collected while the gaseous stream is separated and directed to a water displacement flowmeter (2 L XMI, GN instruments, China).

The trim heater and main reactor sections are heated with six independently controlled 500 W heating tapes and the corresponding power input is electronically logged together with 12 temperature and six pressure measurement points. A schematic overview of the WO reactor with the measurement points is shown in Fig. 1.

2.2. Wet oxidation experiments

The WO experiments were performed at residence times between 12 and 45 min, reaction temperatures of 350 and 365 °C and system pressures of 180 and 200 bar, respectively. The residence time was considered as the time inside the reactor from feed to collection section and was calculated based on the reactor volume, pump flow rate and water density at the temperature and pressure present in each reactor section. Different oxygen equivalent ratios were provided in the range of 0.5–2 times the stoichiometric requirements. The oxidant demand was calculated based on the initial COD of the HTL-AP fraction. Two different sources of oxidant were studied, air and hydrogen peroxide with a considered oxygen content of 21 vol% and 47 vol%, respectively. Hydrogen peroxide was selected as an alternative to mimic the use of pure oxygen and was mixed with HTL-AP in the required ratio just before starting the experiment. The dilution factor, as well as the produced water from H₂O₂ decomposition was considered for this

Fig. 1. Wet Oxidation reactor scheme with measurement points (T_i – temperature, P_i – pressure).

calculation and the following analytical results. The air compressor section was not used when hydrogen peroxide WO was performed.

The WO trials started with preheating the reactor to the desired temperature by circulating water and air or water only at the required flow rates, depending on the oxidant applied. As soon as steady state conditions were reached, a blank window of 15 min was recorded for validation of the temperature profile inside the reactor. The WO test began subsequently by introducing HTL-AP to the system, allowing it to run for twice the residence time before starting the product collection. At least two gas samples were taken towards the end of product collection time for analysis. The WO-AP samples were stored at 4 °C for further analysis.

2.3. Analysis and calculations

HTL-AP and WO-AP samples were analyzed for COD, total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (TN), ammonium and volatile fatty acid (VFA) content. For COD and ammonium, Merck spectroquant test kits were employed (COD: 1.14541.0001; ammonium: 1.00683.0001). TOC and TN analysis was performed using a FORMACS^{HT-1} TOC/TN Analyzer (Skalar, Netherlands). VFA concentrations were quantified using a GC-FID (Model 6890N, Agilent Technologies, USA) with a HP-INNOWAX column (30 m, 0.25 μ m, 0.25 mm ID, Agilent Technologies, USA). VFAs quantified using external standard calibration curves were acetic acid, propanoic acid, isobutyric acid, butyric acid, isovaleric acid, valeric acid, isohexanoic acid and hexanoic acid.

Removal rates were calculated according to Eq. (1), with X denoting for COD and TOC concentration in mg/L, respectively.

$$X_{\text{removal}}[\%] = \frac{X_{\text{initial}} - X_{\text{end}}}{X_{\text{initial}}} * 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

The WO gas was analyzed with a GC-FID/TCD (Model 8890, Agilent Technologies, USA) with a HP-PLOT Q PT column (30 m, 0.53 mm, 40 μ m) and a mole sieve column (30 m, 0.53 mm, 50 μ m), argon as carrier gas, air and hydrogen as FID detector gas and argon as TCD detector gas. Gas components analyzed were carbon dioxide, nitrogen, oxygen, hydrogen, hydrocarbons, methane and carbon monoxide.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. HTL-AP characteristics

The HTL-AP utilized in this experimental campaign was produced in the pilot scale continuous HTL plant at Aarhus University, Denmark [27]. The specific HTL-AP was obtained from a mixture of 50 % cattle manure and 50 % straw based on dry weight with a slurry DM content of 14 %. The slurry was processed at a reaction temperature of 325 °C and a feeding rate of 50 kg/h, leading to a residence time of approximately 20 min. The HTL-AP was gravimetrically separated from bio-crude, centrifuged and stored at ambient conditions until further use. The characterization of HTL-AP is shown in Table 1.

The HTL-AP contains high organic loading, evidenced by COD, TOC and TN values. The carbon content of VFAs accounts to 23 % of TOC, nitrogen from ammonium corresponds to 9 % of TN. We observed HTL-AP as an unstable side product, and characteristics changed with time. The analyses of the studied HTL-AP were performed within 6 and 12 months after HTL production. The given characterization includes the results of both analyses and therefore shows a large standard deviation.

Table 1

HTL-AP from HTL of a 50 %–50 % mixture of cattle manure and straw at 325 °C characterization.

	[mg/L]	HTL-AP	± STDEV
COD		46,988	1325
TOC		15,612	508
TN		963	7
NH ₄ ⁺		118	18
pH		4.30	0.02
Acetic Acid		7259.5	215.9
Propanoic Acid		865.1	26.8
Isobutyric Acid		108.8	0.2
Butyric Acid		158.5	88.4
Isovaleric Acid		111.4	3.0
Isohexanoic Acid		67.2	17.6
Hexanoic Acid		168.9	85.1

3.2. Effect of residence time

The effect of varying residence time, between 12 and 45 min, was studied at constant reaction temperature of 350 °C and stoichiometric oxidant supply as air. The efficiency of WO is assessed by the effectiveness to remove organic species, indicated through COD and TOC removal.

Both COD and TOC removal increased with residence time as shown in Fig. 2A, reaching 83.2 % and 85.5 % at 45 min, respectively. At 12 min, removal efficiencies of 64.5 % (COD) and 65.6 % (TOC) suggest rapid degradation of organics to carbon dioxide and low-molecular-weight intermediates. Similar trends were observed by Silva Thomsen et al. [26] for WO of HTL-AP from sewage sludge, achieving 95.3 % COD and 91.8 % TOC removal at 49.5 min, and by Vadlamudi et al. [25], who reported 85–90 % removal for poultry manure-derived HTL-AP at 350 °C and 30 min with pure oxygen.

VFAs, particularly acetic acid, play a key role as stable intermediates in WO. Fig. 2B shows a peak of the VFA-carbon fraction in TOC at 62.2 % at a residence time of 23 min before declining to 19.6 % at 45 min, suggesting that higher molecular-weight VFAs were oxidized, while acetic acid was formed up to a residence time of 23 min (Fig. 2C). Acetic acid is regarded as a refractory intermediate and needs harsh process conditions to be oxidized to carbon dioxide [19]. As proposed by Debellefontaine et al. [18], organic components dissolved in the AP are degraded during complex oxidation steps to acetic acid, however, higher oxidation rates were observed at temperatures above 320 °C [28]. Even though the studied reaction temperature exceeded the indicated literature temperature, an initial accumulation of acetic acid at lower residence time is suggested due to partial oxidation reactions of organic components. Only sufficiently long residence times (>23 min) lead to a decline in acetic acid concentration. Silva Thomsen et al. [26] also observed acetic acid peaking at 1.5 times its initial concentration between 7 and 27 min before degrading to 0.5 times its original value, while Vadlamudi et al. [25] reported stable acetic acid levels at 30 min, with VFA-carbon accounting for ~70 % of TOC.

Fig. 2. Oxidation efficiency in respect to COD and TOC (A), TOC removal and VFA fraction (B), the fate of three selected VFAs (C) and TN and ammonium fraction (D) at different residence times and 350 °C reaction temperature.

Nitrogen-containing organics degraded primarily to ammonium (Fig. 2D), increasing its fraction in TN from 10 % to up to 98.6 % at 45 min, while TN decreased by 25 %, likely due to ammonia volatilization as previously observed [26]. Literature findings confirm similar ammonium fractions in TN, exceeding 70 % at 350 °C [25,26]. The ammonium increase in WO-AP offers potential for recovery in downstream processes for further utilization in e.g. fertilizer application [29].

Considering post WO benefits such as CO₂ utilization, acetic acid and ammonium recovery, while keeping in mind the thermal integration potential of WO with HTL, the experimental data shows that the optimum lies between residence times of 12–23 min. After such time the additional COD removal is moderate, acetic acid is consumed and importantly the reactor size would increase significantly with the increasing residence times, despite advantages in high ammonium selectivity. Hence residence times of 12 and 23 min were investigated further for oxidant supply ratios. However, if ammonium recovery would be the primary focus, longer residence times should be considered.

3.3. Effect of oxygen supply and applied oxidant

Previously investigated WO parameters are oxidant type, and the amount of oxidant supplied to the system which impacts cost, energy use (gas compression) and byproduct gas management. Using air as an oxidant introduces nitrogen, requiring higher gas flow rates, increasing compression costs and diluting the off-gas, making potential downstream carbon dioxide utilization less efficient. The enhanced gas flow also accelerates the rate of vaporization, as water vapor is carried away more efficiently. However, increased vaporization consumes thermal energy from the system, causing a reduction in adiabatic reactor temperature. This lowers oxidation efficiency compared to the use of pure oxygen [18].

Pure oxygen avoids nitrogen dilution but is more expensive due to production and compression costs. Hydrogen peroxide, a liquid oxidant, simplifies compression and feeding compared to gaseous streams and

eliminates gas phase transfer limitations, though at higher costs [21]. Optimizing stoichiometric oxygen supply minimizes excess off-gas, enhances energy efficiency and reduces superfluous oxidant feed. Hence, we investigated the impact of oxidant type (air vs. hydrogen peroxide) and oxygen supply on WO performance, focusing on oxidation efficiency and potential use for byproduct recovery.

Previous studies have exclusively used oxidants in stoichiometric supply or excess to provide enough oxygen for the WO reaction. The oxidant applied in non-catalytic WO of HTL-AP was mostly pure oxygen for batch experiments or air for continuous reactions [10,25,26]. WO with hydrogen peroxide in batch experiments was investigated for different types of wastewaters [30–33]. Furthermore, promoted wet air oxidation together with hydrogen peroxide showed improvement for oxidation performance [19,22,34]. In the present study, the range of oxygen supplied to the system varied between 0.5 and 2 times the initial COD. Two different oxidants were chosen: air and 35 wt% hydrogen peroxide. All analytical results for WO with hydrogen peroxide were corrected for dilution due to the concentration of hydrogen peroxide and produced water from decomposition. The WO experiments with air were performed at residence times of 12 min and 23 min and reaction temperature of 350 °C. COD and TOC removal as a function of the supplied oxygen equivalents in form of air and hydrogen peroxide at different residence times are shown in Fig. 3.

At 12 min, an increase in COD removal to 58.8 % was observed from 0.5 to 1.0 stoichiometric oxygen provided, while further increase to double the amount of oxygen equivalent did not show any effect. At 23 min, the COD removal showed a plateau between 63.7 and 65.1 % between 0.6 and 2.0 times the stoichiometric demand, indicating no improvement in oxidation efficiency with increased supply of oxygen. During this WO test at 23 min, the air flow reached an overall oxidant supply of 0.6 the stoichiometric requirements due to fluctuations. The results show no advantage using air in stoichiometric excess for improving oxidation efficiency. The absence of enhanced oxidation efficiency by increased oxygen equivalent supplied to the continuous WO system is most likely due to diffusion and reaction kinetics limitations. Oxygen availability above stoichiometric requirements can become irrelevant if reaction rates are limited by mass transfer or kinetics in the AP at given process conditions [16,19,20]. Excess air supply has minimal effect, if the AP is saturated with oxygen.

WO can be influenced by nitrogen as primary and inert compound of air. Debellefontaine et al. [18] reported a dependency of the COD removal based on the oxidant flowrate, showing an optimum of the stoichiometric ratio of 0.5 for WO with air at 280 °C and 110 bar. For WO with pure oxygen, higher COD removals were achieved with an optimal oxidant stoichiometric ratio of 1.

Differences in oxidation efficiency between the use of air or hydrogen peroxide can also be attributed to varied mechanisms of oxygen activation and physicochemical properties of the respective oxidants [19,35]. Gaseous oxidants, such as air or oxygen, require multiple reaction steps to generate hydroxyl radicals, whereas hydrogen peroxide thermally decomposes directly into these highly reactive species via

scission of O-O bond, working as free radical promoter [21,34]. Since hydroxyl radicals form within the liquid phase, they immediately interact with the organic components present in the aqueous effluent.

In the initial phase of WO with hydrogen peroxide, H_2O_2 decomposes thermally into hydroxyl radicals, which rapidly oxidize organic species present in wastewater [36]. This radical-driven oxidation occurs in the early stage of the reaction and is expected to accelerate organic degradation, as these free radicals exhibit a strong oxidation potential [22]. With progression of the reaction, hydroxyl radicals undergo secondary reactions to less reactive HO_2 radicals, dimerization to hydrogen peroxide and finally decomposition to molecular oxygen and water [37]. Over long timescale of the reaction, molecular oxygen becomes the dominant oxidizing agent and continues the degradation reaction of remaining organics [36,37].

Although the initial aggressive radical contribution of hydroxyl radicals is absent in WO with pure oxygen, O_2 produced from thermal decomposition eventually governs the overall oxidation process. Therefore, the oxidation efficiency of WO at prolonged residence times with hydrogen peroxide is assumed to mimic the use of pure oxygen gas. In the present campaign, hydrogen peroxide was chosen as pure gaseous oxygen substitute due to health and safety constrictions in the laboratory. The use of hydrogen peroxide for future industrial WO implementation is not realistic or suggested due to cost [21].

Fig. 4 shows the TOC and corresponding VFA-carbon concentration for WO with air and hydrogen peroxide. For air, TOC remained stable regardless of oxygen supply, with VFA-carbon also relatively constant, contributing to 67–72 % of TOC at 12 min residence time and 60–79 % at 23 min residence time. For hydrogen peroxide, both TOC and VFA-carbon decreased with more oxidant, while the share of VFA in TOC remained at around 80 %. In the initial HTL-AP, around 80 % of the carbon related to VFAs was acetic acid, 10 % propanoic acid and 10 % C_4 – C_7 VFAs, respectively. C_4 – C_7 VFAs were completely oxidized except at the mildest WO process conditions of 12 min residence time and 0.5 times the oxygen demand in form of air. The share of carbon in form of acetic acid rose to a maximum of around 97 % of the total VFAs with the remainder being propanoic acid.

WO with hydrogen peroxide seems to enhance the overall oxidation efficiency when supplying stoichiometric or excess oxygen equivalents. Therefore, higher removal of TOC and specifically VFA intermediates are observed at similar conditions compared to WO with air. This trend can be explained with an improved availability of oxidant species (hydroxyl radicals or molecular oxygen from thermal H_2O_2 decomposition) in the liquid phase. Applying air as an oxidation agent introduces a large nitrogen flow, which can influence the gas solubility and therefore the overall oxidation efficiency in WO [18]. Acetic acid is the refractory main intermediate WO product, which is generated in this process. With increasing severity of the process, the degradation of acetic acid is favoured. In Fig. 5 the relative concentration of acetic acid is shown, to track the generation and degradation of acetic acid for WO with air and hydrogen peroxide.

When using air as oxidant, acetic acid concentration remained

Fig. 3. COD (A) and TOC (B) removal at 350 °C for varying supply of oxygen (as air and hydrogen peroxide) and residence times.

Fig. 4. TOC removal and VFA fraction at 12 min (A) and 23 min (B) for varying supply of oxygen equivalents with air and 23 min for varying supply of oxygen equivalents with hydrogen peroxide (C) at 350 °C reaction temperature.

Fig. 5. Concentration of acetic acid during WO process with different oxidants at 23 min residence time and 350 °C reaction temperature.

constant at sub-stoichiometric oxygen supply. The generation of acetic acid was observed at stoichiometric ratio or above, showing increases up to approximately 9 g/L. This content of acetic acid remained stable until two times the stoichiometric oxygen supplied. For hydrogen peroxide on the contrary, the maximum concentration of acetic acid occurred at 0.5 and 0.8 of the stoichiometric oxygen demand, yielding an increase of around 11 g/L. The value decreased to similar acetic acid concentrations as for air at stoichiometric conditions and further decreased at excess oxygen supply. WO appears more efficient in terms of organic removal using hydrogen peroxide compared to air with stoichiometric or excess oxygen supply. However, if the aim is to maximize VFA concentrations, sub-stoichiometric hydrogen peroxide supply is favorable.

The formation and degradation of acetic acid during WO depends on the applied oxidant. Using air, acetic acid accumulation occurs primarily at stoichiometric oxygen supply and remains stable, suggesting a slower radical formation process that limits further degradation to carbon dioxide and water [19]. In contrast, WO with hydrogen peroxide leads to a peak in acetic acid concentration at sub-stoichiometric conditions, followed by a decline at higher oxidant supply. At sub-stoichiometric oxidant supply, the initial rapid decomposition of hydrogen peroxide at the beginning of the reaction might degrade larger molecules into smaller ones without final oxidation to carbon dioxide, therefore promoting the formation of stable intermediates such as acetic acid and resulting in higher residual TOC compared to air. This explanation can be supported by the lower fraction of non-VFA related carbon of WO with sub-stoichiometric hydrogen peroxide than for air WO at same

conditions (cf. Fig. 4). With increasing supply of oxidant, thermally decomposed hydrogen peroxide would lead to an increased share of molecular oxygen. As a result, WO with hydrogen peroxide achieves more efficient organic removal at stoichiometric or excess oxygen supply, whereas sub-stoichiometric conditions favour the accumulation of acetic acid.

The effect of the supplied amount of oxygen and the oxidant used to the formation of ammonium in the liquid phase is shown in Fig. 6. For air as oxidant and a residence time of 12 min, an increase in ammonium concentration with increasing oxygen supply was observed, yielding a maximum of 698 mg/L at 2.0 times the stoichiometric equivalent. Correspondingly, the fraction of ammonium within TN increased to a maximum of 75.7 %. At 23 min a similar trend can be seen, the ammonium concentrations increased slightly with higher oxygen supply up to 743 mg/L at 2.0 stoichiometric equivalent. The share of ammonium yielded up to 81.9 % in these conditions, the reduction of TN with around 25 % is in the same range as for 12 min residence time. TN reduction could be due to the release of ammonia to the gas phase, as already described by Silva Thomsen et al. [26].

For WO with hydrogen peroxide at 23 min, the overall ammonium concentration after WO process reached similar values independent of the supplied stoichiometric oxygen equivalent and yielded around 460 mg/L. TN was reduced by 32–36 % in the studied range. When comparing the two different oxidants applied, a higher reduction in TN and lower concentration levels of ammonium were observed for WO with hydrogen peroxide compared to WO with air at same conditions. The share of nitrogen in form of ammonium in TN accounted for 58.1–61.2 % for WO with hydrogen peroxide, which was significantly lower than when using air as oxidant at same conditions. A higher share of N-containing components was degraded to ammonium with air as oxidant at comparable process conditions, indicating more efficient oxidation.

The differences in TN removal and ammonium fraction between WO performed with air and hydrogen peroxide remain unclear and require further investigation. WO-AP samples derived from air oxidation have slightly higher pH (around pH 5.1) than those from hydrogen peroxide oxidation (around pH 4.7), making it counterintuitive that WO with hydrogen peroxide achieves higher TN removal and ammonium concentrations, considering the ammonium-ammonia equilibrium. Ammonia stripping due to higher overall gas flow for WO with air may contribute to TN removal, however it does not explain the higher TN removals observed with hydrogen peroxide. Oxidation of N-containing species to nitrate or nitrogen is unlikely under given conditions or the absence of a suitable catalyst [18,38]. The observed TN loss is therefore assumed to be due to the volatilization of ammonia to the gas phase, as already reported elsewhere [26].

3.4. Effect of reaction temperature

Reaction temperature has a significant effect on the WO process of HTL-AP and has been broadly studied in the range of 200–350 °C for

Fig. 6. TN and ammonium share for different supplied oxygen equivalents in form of air at residence times of 12 min (A) and 23 min (B) and supplied oxygen equivalents in form of hydrogen peroxide at a residence time of 23 min (C).

batch and continuous operation [10,25,26]. Operating at WO temperatures in excess of 350 °C are of interest when performing an integrated HTL-WO process with an HTL reaction temperature at 350 °C in order to have a temperature gradient to achieve an autothermal HTL process. Hence this section investigates the effect of slightly higher temperatures on the typical HTL temperature of 350 °C but still staying below the critical temperature (374 °C), to avoid a supercritical process where corrosion becomes an increasing process concern [39].

Fig. 7A shows COD and TOC removal at 350 and 365 °C. Increasing the reaction temperature from 350 to 365 °C led to marginally improved oxidation efficiency. COD removals increased with higher reaction temperature from 71.8 % to 76.1 % and TOC removal from 71.3 % to 73.4 %. This observation is in line with previous results showing a trend of enhanced oxidation efficiency with increasing reaction temperatures [10,25,26].

Changes in TOC and VFA-carbon concentration are presented in Fig. 7B. A reduction in VFA-carbon was observed at higher temperatures, showing a degradation of the oxidation intermediates at harsher conditions. At 350 °C, VFA accounts for 77.7 % of the overall TOC, which reduces to 70.5 % at 365 °C reaction temperature. C₄ – C₇ VFAs were completely oxidized, the share of carbon related to propanoic acid was slightly reduced. Carbon related to acetic acid was removed at higher reaction temperatures. This trend is supported by previous findings, stating that the oxidation reaction pathways shift towards total oxidation with harsher reaction temperatures [18].

The effect of the reaction temperature on the fate of N-containing species and the generation of ammonium is shown in Fig. 7C. The post-WO TN concentrations were reduced to similar values within standard deviation at around 600 mg/L. The overall share of ammonium in TN reached comparable values of approximately 60 % for 350 °C and 365 °C reaction temperature. Hence the overall increase in temperature to 365 °C appears to be a viable solution to increase the heat output and integration with HTL.

3.5. Gas analysis

The off-gas produced in the WO process was analyzed to determine its suitability for further utilization for e.g. carbon sequestration or power-2-x applications. Its composition is especially important when considering downstream gas cleaning processes for such processes. The off-gas composition from hydrogen peroxide WO is shown in Table 2 and primarily consisted of carbon dioxide, derived from complete oxidation of organic species, under sub-stoichiometric conditions.

As oxygen supply increased to stoichiometric ratios or beyond, the share of carbon dioxide decreased to 54 %, while oxygen level rose. This suggests that almost all oxidant species generated from hydrogen peroxide thermal decomposition were largely consumed in oxidation processes. For higher stoichiometric share, incomplete utilization of oxidant species occurs, and oxygen levels rose due to formation of oxygen and water from complete H₂O₂ thermal decomposition [22]. This was observed in the increased oxygen fraction of up to 44 % at 1.5 times the COD. These findings indicated that WO with hydrogen peroxide in stoichiometric level or excess did not lead to complete consumption of the oxidant but resulted in oxygen accumulation and off-gas dilution.

Using air as oxidant introduced a large fraction of inert nitrogen into the process, increasing the overall gas flow and significantly diluting the off-gas. The results in Table 3 comparing the gas composition under sub-stoichiometric and stoichiometric air supply show similar results, with nitrogen as the main component (around 79 %) and carbon dioxide as

Table 2
Gas composition from hydrogen peroxide WO.

	Stoichiometric O ₂ equivalent in form of hydrogen peroxide [–]			
	0.5	0.8	1.0	1.5
CO ₂	97.0 %	97.5 %	84.3 %	53.9 %
CO	0.6 %	0.5 %	0.4 %	0.0 %
H ₂	2.3 %	1.6 %	0.6 %	2.3 %
N ₂	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %
O ₂	0.1 %	0.5 %	14.7 %	43.7 %

Fig. 7. (A) Oxidation efficiency (B) TOC removal and VFA portion and (C) TN and ammonium share at 23 min residence time and stoichiometric supply of oxygen (as H₂O₂).

Table 3
Gas composition from air WO.

	Stoichiometric O ₂ equivalent in form of air [-] (23 min residence time)		Residence time [min] (stoichiometric O ₂ equivalent)		
	0.6	1.0	12	23	30
CO ₂	18.3 %	12.0 %	12.6 %	12.0 %	12.5 %
CO	1.4 %	0.9 %	1.5 %	0.9 %	0.9 %
H ₂	0.5 %	0.2 %	0.1 %	0.2 %	0.3 %
N ₂	79.2 %	79.0 %	78.8 %	79.0 %	79.0 %
O ₂	0.6 %	8.0 %	7.0 %	8.0 %	7.3 %

oxidation product.

Also for air, almost all oxygen was consumed in sub-stoichiometric conditions. This was already indicated by reaching maximum COD removal at provided oxidant ratio. Providing the stoichiometric demand in form of air led to a fraction of 8 % oxygen in the off-gas, which was lower than for hydrogen peroxide at comparable conditions. Additionally, the gas composition remained consistent across the residence time from 12 to 30 min.

A small fraction of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, and traces of methane were detected in all WO gas samples. These gases may have been produced either by the thermal decomposition of organic compounds present in the water or by secondary reactions between the gases and water, such as the water-gas shift reaction, reforming, and methanation. Although these reactions are typically catalytic, the presence of metals in the reactor walls and the high excess of water could allow their production.

4. Conclusion

The present study investigated continuous wet oxidation of HTL-AP derived from a mixture of cow manure and wheat straw with focus on oxidant supply and future integration possibilities with HTL. High TOC removal with a maximum 85.5 % at 45 min and 350 °C reaction temperature was achieved, although residence longer than 12–23 min showed little benefit. A moderate increase in oxidation efficiency together with a decrease in VFA content was observed for increasing reaction condition severities. By adjusting residence time, the specific target of the WO operation (maximizing byproduct recovery vs. maximizing oxidation efficiency) can be regulated. The results show a relatively stable process when adjusting the reaction temperature, which gives rise to a more flexible temperature operation range in integrated HTL-WO systems with a focus on autothermal operation.

Increasing oxygen supply in the form of air showed little effect to oxidation efficiency and the increase of VFA and ammonium share to TOC and TN, respectively. The supply of hydrogen peroxide showed higher COD and TOC removals when exceeding 0.5 times the stoichiometric demand compared to air. Differences in the results between the studied oxidants highlight the impact of oxidant type and supplied oxygen ratio towards the overall WO process, considering oxidation efficiency and byproduct recovery potential. Providing sub-stoichiometric oxidant shows advantages regarding cost, byproduct formation and off-gas composition, while maintaining similar results for oxidation efficiency compared to stoichiometric or excess supply.

Results of the gas-composition showed an almost pure carbon dioxide stream for WO with sub-stoichiometric supply of hydrogen peroxide and an increase of residual oxygen for stoichiometric and higher supply. WO with air produced a gas mainly (79 %) composed of nitrogen. The results show the importance of oxidant choice when considering gas cleaning and downstream carbon dioxide utilization. Overall, it can be concluded that the optimal WO process conditions for thermal integration with HTL and byproduct recovery lie at 350–365 °C, 12–23 min and most importantly, sub-stoichiometric oxygen supply.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Carolyn Eva Schuck: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Giulia Zoppi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Konstantinos Anastasakis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Patrick Biller:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work the authors used GPT-4 in order to improve readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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